

NUTRITIONAL STATUS IN SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Childhood and adolescent malnutrition can result in less than ideal growth, repercussions that span generations, and a higher chance of developing chronic illnesses as an adult. Since the majority of current interventions focus on promoting healthy nutrition, little is known regarding the prevalence and causes of malnutrition in Uzbekistan among children aged 5 to 19. In order to provide data to guide future policy direction, we evaluated the nationwide prevalence, trends, and risk factors related with undernutrition among children in Uzbekistan aged 5 to 19.*

Keywords: *iron deficiency, Nutritional status, obesity.*

Relevance. The prevalence and trends of nutritional status indicators among children and adolescents in Uzbekistan between the ages of 5 and 19 are being analyzed and interpreted for the first time at the regional and national levels in this study. In addition to stunting and micronutrient deficiencies, this study issues a severe warning regarding the appearance and rising trends of overweight and obesity among Uzbek adolescents aged 5 to 19. One of the main priorities for lowering the burden of child mortality and associated diseases is the prevention and treatment of malnutrition. Late childhood and adolescence are crucial times for the development of health-related behaviors and sensitivity to nutritional determinants, and they should be acknowledged as an opportunity window for treating eating disorders that last a lifetime.

All parts of the world, especially wealthy nations, are impacted by the twin burden of malnutrition. A paradigm shift from the prevention and management of malnutrition to a more comprehensive, two-pronged strategy is necessary in light of the patterns found in this study, which suggest the necessity to include particular interventions to address different eating disorders. Future intervention/policy goals for sustaining a healthy population weight should not be limited to prevention and treatment alone, as malnutrition and overweight/obesity coexist.

The purpose of this study. This indicator's goal is to quantify chronic malnutrition and nutritional imbalance that leads to undernutrition (measured by stunting and underweight) and overweight. The frequency and trends of nutritional status indicators as well as socioeconomic and demographic risk factors linked to malnutrition are presented in this study for children and adolescents in the Republic of Uzbekistan who are between the ages of 5 and 19. Additionally, this is the first investigation to evaluate the double burden of malnutrition by taking into account deficiencies in both macro and micronutrients. According to our estimates, the region's undernutrition burden is expected to stay at little over one-quarter of children (27.9%), while the overnutrition burden is expected to be 15.6%.

By 2030, it is anticipated that micronutrient deficiencies, such as iron deficiency anemia and vitamin A insufficiency, will decline. Our analysis's conclusions indicate that undernutrition and overnutrition are widespread in Uzbekistan.

Materials and methods of research. The best global measure of children's health is their nutritional status. Growth evaluation not only reveals disparities in social development but also serves as a tool for assessing a child's health and nutritional state. One of the global sustainable

development goals (SDGs) is to reduce child malnutrition by 2025. Other indicators of sustainable development include proper nutrition and health in the early years of life. Undernutrition (such as underweight, wasting, and stunting) and overnutrition (such as overweight and obesity) are both included in the wide term "malnutrition". A serious public health issue, particularly in poorer nations, is malnutrition.

Overnutrition and undernutrition have negative health impacts at every stage of life. Undernutrition can be caused by a lack of availability to food, illness, improper child nutrition, restricted access to medical care, or any combination of these. Children's development and growth are undoubtedly influenced by a number of things. While some of these factors—like sickness and nutritional status—have direct effects on a child's growth and development, others—like poverty and parents' lack of literacy—have indirect consequences because they contribute to low food intake and disease. A significant public health issue at the moment is the rising incidence of obesity worldwide and the resulting socioeconomic cost.

Obesity and overweight in children are linked to a higher risk of negative health outcomes, such as non-communicable diseases including diabetes, high blood pressure, and heart disease. Improving the nutritional status of newborns and children is a major problem for any nation's public healthcare system and a crucial item on the public health agenda for ensuring the health of future generations. Using data from national surveys, nutritional status determination, trend analysis, and health indicator forecasting—particularly for vulnerable groups, particularly children—are essential for both policymakers and the development of effective treatments.

The rapid nutritional transition, urbanization, and shifting food consumption patterns are all contributing factors to the rising incidence of obesity and overweight in children and the declining prevalence of undernutrition (underweight and stunting) in children, according to national surveys carried out in Iran. Malnutrition is still far more common in several Iranian provinces than the national average, though. The nutritional status of young children has probably been impacted by the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic and its implications on food security and access to healthcare facilities, particularly in vulnerable groups. International reports state that the COVID-19 epidemic has put millions of people's food security at risk as a health emergency.

Even though the implications of this crisis are still impossible to anticipate with precision, adverse outcomes are to be expected for vulnerable groups, including children and pregnant and lactating women, particularly those who experienced food insecurity prior to the epidemic. Infant iron insufficiency is an issue that is underdiagnosed and undertreated, and it is linked to cognitive impairment. Due mostly to increasing breastfeeding and the use of iron-fortified feeding formulae, the prevalence of iron deficiency anemia (IDA) in the first year of life has significantly decreased in developed nations. However, recent research on children aged 1-2 in Uzbekistan has shown that the prevalence of iron deficiency and IDA is 30% and >10%, respectively.

Throughout their lives, children between the ages of one and two consume less iron each day than any other age group. In the first two years of life, IDA is linked to poor mental and psychomotor development. These deficiencies persist and may even be irreversible even after anemia is corrected. The fact that iron deficiency is linked to higher absorption of lead is another compelling argument for preventing it in children, particularly in those between the ages of one and two. Previously thought to be innocuous, blood lead levels below 10 µg/L cause lead-related

cognitive impairment. Infants currently have an unacceptable rate of iron deficiency and IDA, particularly in lower socioeconomic groups.

Due to increased lead absorption and injury to the central nervous system from iron deficiency itself, these early children are twice as likely to experience neurodevelopmental problems. Iron deficiency and IDA in many infants seem to be prevented by the current screening and treatment guidelines for IDA in Uzbekistan and other affluent nations. Similarly, the current body of medical literature underrecognized or under addresses the issue of intellectual and psychomotor developmental problems. After stopping breastfeeding or iron-fortified formula, the author suggests preventing iron deficiency and iron-induced anemia (IDA) by administering extra daily doses of 10 mg of elemental iron using iron-fortified vitamins, iron drops, or iron-fortified liquids.

We gathered information from published studies and nationally representative surveys on the determinants (odds ratio or risk ratio) and burden (prevalence or mean) of nutritional status indicators. Underweight, overweight, obesity, stunting, thinness, anemia, and deficiencies in micronutrients such as vitamin A, vitamin B, vitamin C, and vitamin D are among the study results. We adhered to the outcome variable definitions found in the original research of the included papers.

According to pooled analysis, children from lower-income families, those whose parents had less education, and female children had a considerably greater prevalence of anemia. Similarly, children from poorer households, those with secondary or lower levels of maternal and paternal education, and those who reported unhealthy eating habits had a considerably higher prevalence of stunting and thinness.

In the majority of SEA nations, females were shown to be less thin but more stunted than males throughout time. While several factors, such as a higher level of education for both parents, wealthier households, increased media consumption, unhealthy eating habits, and physical inactivity, were significantly linked to an increase in overweight or obesity, only lifestyle factors (time spent on media and unhealthy eating habits) were statistically significant with an increase in prevalence for underweight. Low weight-for-age, low height-for-age, and high weight-for-height indicator prevalences are calculated using an international standard (the WHO Child Growth Standards).

In order to address the double burden of malnutrition that affects populations worldwide, the International Pediatric Association (IPA), the Standing Committee on Nutrition of the United Nations System (SCN), and the International Union of Nutritional Sciences (IUNS) have formally endorsed the use of the WHO standards, characterizing them as an effective tool for detecting and monitoring both undernutrition and overweight. Since the impact of ethnic or genetic characteristics on young children is deemed negligible, the WHO guidelines may be applied to all children up to the age of five. Less than two standard deviations below the WHO Child Growth Standards median are considered low weight for age and low height for age.

More than two standard deviations above the WHO Child Growth Standards median are considered high weight for height. The number of children analyzed and the prevalence of stunting, underweight, wasting, obesity, and overweight were taken from the reports. The indicators were computed using raw data from the Health Research Institute and the online version of the WHO Anthro Survey Analyzer software, after removing outliers ($+5 < \text{Weight-for-Length/Height} < -5$),

because there was insufficient information on the percentage of overweight and obese children in the 2010 survey.

ENI and accessible data on exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) up to 6 months of age from the pertinent national reports were analyzed to assess nutritional status. Only food expenses were taken into account in this study, not household expenses as a whole. Because household food spending is a good indicator of household (rather than individual) food consumption, and because household size, member age, and gender all have an impact on food expenditure, adult male equivalent (AME) was employed to account for these factors. Mean monthly consumption based on AME and weighted pricing were the two main variables that were computed and extracted for each province during the study year in order to determine ENI.

ENI was then computed by dividing the cost of each food category in the ideal food basket by the household expenditure on that food group. The R Studio software suite was used to perform these analyses.

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends using linear mixed-effects models to predict stunting, underweight, and wasting status for 2020, as well as to identify trends in anthropometric indices over the past few decades. The prevalence of overweight and obesity could not be estimated since national surveys did not provide enough information on the pertinent markers. Logit values of HAZ, WHZ, and WAZ were used to establish dependent variables.

Province and study year were included in the basic model; the year-province interaction was also included as a fixed variable. This kind of model is a member of the multilevel model category, which is derived from the restricted maximum likelihood computation. Between 2000 and 2020, the entire model was utilized to estimate the prevalence of malnutrition: back-transformation was employed to estimate the prevalence and the corresponding confidence interval (CI). Additionally, a model that took food security into consideration was built using linear mixed-effects modeling. Province was included as a random variable in this model, whereas the year of study and the food security category (food-secure, moderately insecure, or severely food insecure) were included as fixed effects.

Researches and discussion. Food-insecure provinces continue to have high rates of stunting, underweight, and wasting notwithstanding the decline in malnutrition over the previous three decades. Furthermore, it is conceivable that the prevalence of malnutrition may rise in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and its economic effects, particularly in provinces with food insecurity. In food-insecure areas, the prevalence of stunting, underweight, and wasting is still greater than the national average, even though malnutrition has been declining over the last three decades. Furthermore, it is anticipated that the prevalence of childhood malnutrition would rise in light of the COVID-19 pandemic and the elevated risk of food insecurity, particularly as a result of the global economic downturn.

The identification of high-risk locations can be facilitated by forecasting and modeling the future incidence of malnutrition, highlighting the necessity of developing and implementing efficient local interventions. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that in provinces with high prevalence rates and/or an upward trend in prevalence, factors that contribute to various types of child malnutrition (both under- and over-nutrition) be looked into and identified regionally. In addition to national objectives for attaining sustainable development, regional and provincial planning, design, and implementation of programs are necessary to manage and prevent different forms of malnutrition.

These programs ought to take into account the local causes of overweight and malnutrition, such as mothers' ignorance of proper feeding techniques, feeding children foods low in nutrients, using inappropriate child care, breastfeeding for brief periods of time, not having access to health care, and food insecurity at home. By focusing on interventions that address child malnutrition, nutrition-sensitive interventions should be designed, implemented, and assessed with the goal of reducing poverty and empowering households.

Additionally, data on children's growth status should be continuously and regularly gathered, analyzed, and interpreted through the extension of the food and nutrition surveillance system to all provinces of the nation. Regular reports should be presented to policymakers for the purposes of strategic planning and evaluation of ongoing progress. Prioritizing specific locations and planning interventions require consideration of the COVID-19 pandemic's effects as well as the current state of the economy.

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